

The views expressed are those of the author and do not reflect the official policy or position of the Department of Defense or the U.S. Government

Automated Multi-Physics Reliability-Oriented Layout Design for Multi-Chip Power Modules Using the LAREL Tool

David Agogo-Mawuli, Ekene Gabriel Okafor, Whit Vinson, David Huitink and Alan Mantooh
University of Arkansas
Fayetteville, Arkansas 72701 USA
Email: dsa008@uark.edu

Abstract

As industries advance in electrification, the demand for high-power-density multi-chip power modules (MCPMs) continues to grow. Critical in applications like electric vehicles (EVs), renewable energy systems, and industrial automation, MCPMs must deliver compact, efficient designs while withstanding harsh conditions, including high temperatures, mechanical stresses, and heavy electrical loads. While existing tools such as PowerSynth are effective in optimizing key electrical and thermal performance parameters, they do not incorporate interconnect parametric optimization and detailed assessments, particularly for wire bonds, which are critical to ensuring the long-term reliability of MCPMs. This study introduces the Layout Reliability Tool (LAREL), an extension of PowerSynth that integrates reliability metrics into MCPM optimization. LAREL evaluates critical interconnect factors, such as electromigration and mechanical stress, by automating stress and temperature data extraction from ParaPower. Through a two-stage workflow, LAREL assesses layouts based on wire inductance and lifetime before employing Monte-Carlo sampling and the Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA2) for multi-objective optimization, producing a Pareto front of reliability-driven layouts. By addressing failure risks early in the design process, LAREL enhances MCPM robustness and empowers designers to select optimal configurations. This innovation bridges the gap between performance optimization and reliability evaluation, enabling the development of next-generation MCPMs for power-dense, mission-critical applications.

Key words

Multi-chip Power Modules (MCPMs), Interconnect Reliability, Multi-Physics Analysis, Electromigration-Stress Model, Layout Reliability Tool (LAREL), Wire Inductance Optimization

I. Introduction

System reliability assessment is paramount in the design of multi-chip power modules (MCPMs), particularly as these systems are tasked with meeting the demands of power-dense and mission-critical applications. Reliable operation under extreme conditions necessitates a detailed evaluation of module designs, taking into account material properties, thermal behavior, and mechanical stress interactions [1]. These factors play a crucial role in determining the overall performance and longevity of MCPMs in challenging environments.

A systematic approach is essential to capture the intricate dynamics within the module. This includes evaluating material selection, temperature distribution, and stress

propagation across components. To achieve this, robust multi-physics frameworks are required to extract and analyze the parameters necessary for optimizing the most vulnerable components of the module. Such evaluations ensure that design decisions are informed by a comprehensive understanding of the interdependencies within MCPMs, leading to enhanced reliability and performance [2], [3].

At the heart of this analysis lies the interconnect, particularly wire bonds, which are highly susceptible to failure. Wire bonds, as critical interconnection components, face a unique combination of high temperatures, elevated current densities, and mechanical stresses that drive failure mechanisms such as electromigration-induced voiding and thermomechanical stress accumulation. These risks are further compounded by environmental factors, including

thermal cycling and vibrations, which amplify damage to interconnects and reduce the overall reliability of the MCPM [4], [5], [6]. Despite their critical role, interconnections are often overlooked or inadequately addressed in conventional design workflows [7], [8]. While tools like the Rain tool have advanced reliability assessment by modeling aging processes such as electromigration, thermomigration, and stress migration, they primarily focus on evaluating failure mechanisms under varying conditions using hydrostatic stress abstraction and temperature-dependent criteria [9]. However, the Rain tool does not incorporate the assessment of optimized layout configurations and their impact on interconnect reliability within its framework. This limitation highlights a critical gap in existing methodologies, as the interplay between layout optimization and interconnect reliability is essential for achieving robust designs. Addressing this need requires a framework that integrates multi-physics reliability analyses with an evaluation of how layout configurations influence interconnection performance, paving the way for a more comprehensive design workflow.

To address these challenges, this study introduces the Layout Reliability Tool (LAREL), an innovative extension of PowerSynth that integrates multi-physics reliability metrics into MCPM layout optimization workflows [10], [11]. The contributions of LAREL are:

1. Integration of Multi-Physics Reliability Metrics: Combines electrical, thermal, and mechanical reliability analyses for comprehensive evaluation [12].
2. Layout Optimization for Reliability and Electrical Performance: Assesses multiple MCPM layout configurations, balancing reliability, stress, and thermal considerations with wire inductance to evaluate electrical performance.
3. Physical Parameter Optimization for Wire Bond Interconnects: Refines wire bond parameters to enhance reliability (e.g., electromigration mitigation) and optimize electrical performance using wire inductance [13], [14].

This study highlights the critical need for integrating a multi-physics approach into MCPM design workflows, addressing interconnect reliability as a fundamental component of system longevity. By bridging the gap between performance optimization and reliability evaluation, LAREL represents a significant advancement in developing robust, power-dense MCPMs for mission-critical applications. With its comprehensive methodology, LAREL ensures the viability of next-generation MCPMs in demanding applications such as transportation, renewable energy, and industrial automation.

II. Background

The increasing demand for high-power-density multi-chip

power modules (MCPMs) in applications like electric vehicles, renewable energy systems, and industrial automation underscores the need for reliable, compact, and efficient designs capable of withstanding harsh conditions. While tools like PowerSynth optimize electrical and thermal performance, they often neglect interconnection reliability, particularly for wire bonds, which are prone to failures such as electromigration and thermomechanical stress.

Addressing these challenges requires a multi-physics approach that evaluates material properties, temperature distribution, and stress dynamics to extract critical parameters for optimizing interconnect reliability. Current tools lack the integration of comprehensive reliability metrics, leaving a gap in the design process.

This study introduces a design-for-reliability (DfR) framework through the Layout Reliability Tool (LAREL), extending PowerSynth's capabilities to incorporate multi-physics analyses. By systematically addressing failure mechanisms, LAREL enhances MCPM reliability, meeting the demands of next-generation applications while advancing efficiency and sustainability in power electronics.

II. LAREL Tool Overview

The proposed methodology integrates three key software tools—PowerSynth, ParaPower, and the newly developed Layout Reliability Tool (LAREL)—to address the challenges of MCPM design and interconnect reliability as shown in Fig. 1. Each tool plays a specific role in the multi-stage workflow, combining electrical, thermal, and mechanical analyses to produce robust, reliability-optimized MCPM designs. The following provides a detailed overview of each tool and its role in the process:

Fig. 1. Workflow for Multi-Physics Reliability-Oriented MCPM Design Using PowerSynth, ParaPower, and LAREL.

A. PowerSynth

PowerSynth is the foundational tool used to generate initial MCPM layouts. Designers can define material properties, component geometries, and boundary conditions, ensuring the layouts meet electrical and thermal performance

requirements. These layouts, exported in JSON format, provide a starting point for further analysis and reliability evaluation. PowerSynth’s focus is on achieving performance-oriented designs while preparing data that will be further enriched by reliability-specific parameters[1].

B. ParaPower

ParaPower enhances the workflow by extracting critical parametric results such as stress and temperature distributions for each MCPM component. This step provides a deeper understanding of the module’s thermal and mechanical behavior under operational conditions. The results from ParaPower serve as inputs for the next stage, where interconnect reliability metrics are evaluated in detail. ParaPower ensures that designs are evaluated holistically, considering multi-physics interactions critical for system longevity [12], [15].

C. LAREL

LAREL builds upon the outputs of PowerSynth and ParaPower to focus specifically on interconnection reliability. The tool automates the extraction of stress and temperature data and uses industry-standard models to assess critical interconnect parameters such as wire lifetime and inductance as shown in Fig. 2. LAREL operates in two stages:

Fig. 2. LAREL interface showing wire parameter initialization and global

Stage 1: Stage 1: This stage evaluates MCPM layouts based on key reliability metrics, providing a clear comparison of configurations with minimum interconnect lifetime and maximum inductance. To ensure accuracy and robustness in these evaluations, an electromigration-stress model, previously validated in [8], [14], is employed to analyze the interconnect lifetime. Additionally, a JESD-

compliant model is utilized for wire inductance calculations, as outlined in [13]. These models collectively establish a reliable foundation for assessing MCPM configurations and identifying designs that prioritize reliability and performance.

Stage 2: It uses user-defined interconnect parameter ranges (e.g., wire diameter, loop height, spacing) and applies sampling techniques such as Monte Carlo to generate a diverse set of design variations. These variations are optimized using a multi-objective algorithm, such as Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA2), to produce Pareto-optimal layouts balancing performance and reliability [16].

By integrating these tools into a structured workflow, the methodology addresses the limitations of existing MCPM design processes, particularly in evaluating interconnect reliability. This comprehensive approach ensures the generation of reliability-optimized MCPMs capable of meeting the stringent demands of power-dense, mission-critical applications.

III. Case Studies

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology, practical case studies were conducted using PowerSynth, ParaPower, and LAREL. These studies illustrate LAREL’s capability to evaluate and rank MCPM layouts based on interconnection reliability metrics such as wire lifetime and inductance. The results highlight significant improvements achieved in layout designs, particularly in enhancing wire lifetime and reducing inductance, which are critical for system reliability in mission-critical applications.

A. Ranking Layouts Based on Reliability

The first case study demonstrates LAREL’s ability to systematically rank MCPM layouts using its multi-stage workflow. Starting with PowerSynth-generated layouts, ParaPower extracted stress and temperature data under specific operational conditions. LAREL then evaluated these layouts based on wire inductance and interconnect lifetime. Fig. 3 shows the comparison of layouts, where high-priority configurations exhibit minimal inductance and extended wire lifetime.

Fig. 3. Three layouts selected from generated fixed-sized layouts from PowerSynth.

Fig. 4. Layout ranking chart for which allows for selectivity for more detailed optimization.

As shown in Fig.4, the evaluated layouts are plotted against two primary metrics—minimum interconnect lifetime and maximum wire inductance. The graph illustrates clear distinctions between configurations, enabling designers to identify the most reliable layouts for further refinement.

B. Detailed Reliability Optimization

The second case study focuses on the optimization process in LAREL's Stage 2 workflow. Starting from user-defined input ranges for interconnect parameters (e.g., wire diameter, spacing, and loop height), Monte Carlo sampling generated a diverse set of design variations. The Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA2) was then applied to produce Pareto-optimal solutions that balance wire lifetime and inductance.

Fig. 5. Detailed optimization Pareto-chart showing the routing (position) of the wire bonds from selected Layout C.

Fig. 5 illustrates the Pareto front generated from the optimization process, highlighting configurations that achieve optimal trade-offs between wire lifetime and inductance. This demonstrates LAREL's ability to refine designs systematically, ensuring reliability and performance are both prioritized.

C. Discussion of Results

The case studies showcase LAREL's comprehensive methodology in improving MCPM interconnect reliability. In Case Study 1, LAREL effectively ranked layouts, providing designers with clear metrics for decision-making. In Case Study 2, the tool's optimization capabilities resulted in significant enhancements in both lifetime and inductance, as demonstrated by the Pareto front. Together, these results underline LAREL's potential to address the limitations of traditional MCPM design tools by integrating reliability metrics into the design process.

IV. Conclusion and Future Work

The LAREL presented in this study significantly advances electronic packaging by integrating layout optimization and reliability assessment. By evaluating critical metrics such as electromigration, thermal stress and wire inductance, LAREL provides packaging engineers with a unified platform for optimizing designs holistically and efficiently. The use of advanced techniques like Monte Carlo sampling and the SPEA2 algorithm ensures designs are both high-performing and resilient.

Future work will focus on integrating machine learning to enhance LAREL's predictive capabilities and computational efficiency. By leveraging historical data, machine learning models can identify potential failure mechanisms and provide probabilistic reliability forecasts for novel designs, reducing the need for extensive physical testing. Additionally, machine learning-driven optimization could streamline layout evaluations, accelerating the search for reliable configurations while maintaining accuracy. These advancements would further solidify LAREL's role as an essential tool for addressing the growing complexities of next-generation interconnection designs.

Acknowledgment

The authors thank the Office of Naval Research, National Science Foundation, and University of Arkansas for funding and facility access for the completion of this work. This material is based upon work supported by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) under contract no. FA9550-21-1-0205 and the National Science Foundation (NSF) under grant no. 2014-00555-04. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Office of Naval Research or the National Science Foundation.

References

10, 2025. [Online]. Available:
<https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1571417124781606656>

- [1] T. M. Evans *et al.*, “PowerSynth: A Power Module Layout Generation Tool,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 5063–5078, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2870346.
- [2] X. Zhang, B. Deng, Q. Zhang, Q. Zhang, and G. Bian, “Multi-Physics Simulation of Electromigration in Cu Interconnect,” in *2024 Conference of Science and Technology for Integrated Circuits (CSTIC)*, Mar. 2024, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/CSTIC61820.2024.10531896.
- [3] A. S. Saleh, K. Croes, H. Ceric, I. De Wolf, and H. Zahedmanesh, “A framework for combined simulations of electromigration induced stress evolution, void nucleation, and its dynamics: Application to nano-interconnect reliability,” *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 134, no. 13, 2023, Accessed: Jan. 10, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jap/article/134/13/135102/2914065>
- [4] O. E. Gabriel and D. R. Huitink, “Failure Mechanisms Driven Reliability Models for Power Electronics: A Review,” *Journal of Electronic Packaging*, vol. 145, no. 020801, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1115/1.4055774.
- [5] J. Goehre, M. Schneider-Ramelow, U. Geißler, and K.-D. Lang, “Interface degradation of Al heavy wire bonds on power semiconductors during active power cycling measured by the shear test,” 2010.
- [6] Y. Yang, H. Wang, A. Sangwongwanich, and F. Blaabjerg, “45 - Design for Reliability of Power Electronic Systems,” in *Power Electronics Handbook (Fourth Edition)*, M. H. Rashid, Ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, 2018, pp. 1423–1440. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-811407-0.00051-9.
- [7] Z. Saadatizadeh, M. Sanjabiasasi, D. Agogo-Mawuli, D. Huitink, Y. Peng, and H. A. Mantooh, “Automated Layout Optimization Methods of a Bidirectional DC-DC ZVS Converter Using PowerSynth,” in *2023 IEEE Design Methodologies Conference (DMC)*, Miami, FL, USA: IEEE, Sep. 2023, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/DMC58182.2023.10412521.
- [8] D. Huitink *et al.*, “Factoring Interacting Stress Mechanisms in Design for Reliability of Extreme Environment Power Modules”.
- [9] A. Abbasinasab and M. Marek-Sadowska, “RAIN: a tool for reliability assessment of interconnect networks---physics to software,” in *Proceedings of the 55th Annual Design Automation Conference*, in DAC '18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Jun. 2018, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1145/3195970.3196099.
- [10] Q. Le, T. Evans, Y. Peng, and H. A. Mantooh, “PEEC Method and Hierarchical Approach Towards 3D Multichip Power Module (MCPM) Layout Optimization,” in *2019 IEEE International Workshop on Integrated Power Packaging (IWIPP)*, Apr. 2019, pp. 131–136. doi: 10.1109/IWIPP.2019.8799081.
- [11] I. Al Razi, Q. Le, T. M. Evans, S. Mukherjee, H. A. Mantooh, and Y. Peng, “PowerSynth Design Automation Flow for Hierarchical and Heterogeneous 2.5-D Multichip Power Modules,” *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 8919–8933, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3049776.
- [12] *USArmyResearchLab/ParaPower*. (Oct. 14, 2024). MATLAB. DEVCOM Army Research Laboratory. Accessed: Jan. 11, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/USArmyResearchLab/ParaPower>
- [13] “JESD59.”
- [14] W. Vinson and D. Huitink, “Mechanical stress state consideration for enhanced electromigration life prediction in aluminum wire bonds,” *Microelectronics Reliability*, vol. 149, p. 115185, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.microrel.2023.115185.
- [15] L. M. Boteler, M. C. Fish, and M. S. Berman, “Parametric and Sensitivity Analysis of Power Module Design,” doi: 10.1115/IPACK2019-6592.
- [16] E. Zitzler, “SPEA2: Improving the performance of the strength pareto evolutionary algorithm.” *Technical Report, Computer Engineering and Communication Networks Lab (TIK), Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) Zurich*, 2001, Accessed: Jan.